

A NEW METHOD OF FORMATION OF EUDALENE

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A synthesis of pure eudalene from 5-methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid has been described. The latter has also been prepared by an unambiguous method from 4-methyl-1-hydrindone.

The fundamental naphthalene hydrocarbon eudalene, $C_{14}H_{14}$, first isolated by Ruzicka, Meyer, and Mingazzini (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 8, 363) by the dehydrogenation of a number of natural sesquiterpenes has been definitely shown to be 1-methyl-7-isopropyl-naphthalene by both analytical and synthetical methods (Ruzicka and Mingazzini, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 8, 710; Ruzicka and Stoll, *ibid.*, 923). Its important bearing on the sesquiterpene chemistry is now well established (Ruzicka, "Über Konstitution und Zusammenhänge in der Sesquiterpene reihe", p. 46; also Bradfield, Hegde, Rao and Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 672; Bradfield, Pritchard and Simonsen, *ibid.*, 1937, 761; Bradfield, Penfold and Simonsen, *ibid.*, 1932, 2753; Penfold and Simonsen, *ibid.*, 1939, 87) and a number of independent syntheses of eudalene are on record (Darzens and Levy, *Compt. rend.*, 1932, 194, 2056; Barnett and Sanders, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 434).

The present investigation was undertaken with the object of obtaining an authentic specimen of eudalene required in connection with another investigation, since there exists a considerable discrepancy among previous workers regarding the melting points of the solid derivatives of eudalene (see table below).

TABLE I

Previous authors	Picrate, m.p.	Styphnate, m.p.
Ruzicka, Meyer and Mingazzini	90-92°	119-120°
Darzens and Levy	92.8°	119.8°
Barnett and Sanders	95°	122°
Bradfield, Hegde, Rao and Simonsen	91-92°	117-118°

The starting point in this synthesis was ethyl *o*-xylylmalonate (I, R=Me) which was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate in presence of sodium ethoxide to give (II, R=Me). The latter on hydrolysis and elimination of carbon dioxide afforded *o*-xylylsuccinic acid (III, R=Me), m.p., 172°, which was characterised by an anhydride, anilic acid, and an anil. With concentrated sulphuric acid the acid underwent cyclisation to 5-methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid (IV, R=Me), m.p. 164°.

(I)

(II)

The constitution of (IV, R=Me) is assumed from analogy with cyclisation of benzylsuccinic acid (III, R=H) to the corresponding tetrahydronaphthalene derivative (IV, R=H) (Attwood, Stevenson and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1758; cf. Von Braun, *Ber.*, 1928, 61B, 441). It is quite conceivable, however, that it might be the hydrindone (V).

For our purpose, therefore, it seemed desirable to confirm the constitution of the keto-acid (IV, R=Me) by a rational synthesis as follows:—

4-Methyl-1-hydrindone (VI) (Young, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2704; Mercer and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 292; Plattner and Wyss, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 23, 907), prepared by an improved method from β -*o*-tolylpropionic acid, condenses with ethyl formate in presence of finely divided sodium (cf. Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1851) to give the unstable hydroxymethylene derivative (VII) (cf. Ruhemann and Levy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 2546) which on successive

treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and alkali yields the dicarboxylic acid (VIII), m.p. 172° (cf. Bardhan, *loc. cit.*, Robinson and Rydon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1401). The diethyl ester of (VIII) on treatment with molecular sodium (Titeley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 2572) followed by the action of ethyl bromoacetate gives the hydrindone derivative (IX) in an excellent yield. The later on alkaline hydrolysis affords the tricarboxylic acid (X), m.p. 217-18°.

The diethyl ester of (X) on treatment with sodium followed by hydrolysis of the resulting product with dilute hydrochloric acid furnishes a keto-acid, m.p. 164°, indistinguishable from the tetrahydronaphthalene derivative (IV, R=Me) described above.

The keto-acid on Clemmensen's reduction gives an acid (XI), m.p. 132°. The corresponding ester is treated with an excess of magnesium methyl iodide to give the expected tertiary alcohol (XII) having a characteristic terpene-like smell. The latter on dehydrogenation with selenium at 230-300° for 24 hours gives eudalene, picrate m.p. 93°, styphnate, m.p. 120° (cf. Table I). The regenerated hydrocarbon forms a colourless oil, b. p. 112°/6 mm., d_4^{20} , 0.9740; n_D^{20} , 1.5833; $[R_L]_D$, 63.2.

The physical constants are in good agreement with those recorded by Ruzicka and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) for pure eudalene.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. Synthesis of 5-Methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic Acid (IV, R=Me)

o-Xylylmalonic Ester.—Ethyl malonate (48 g.) was added dropwise to a suspension of finely divided sodium (6.9 g.) in benzene (100 c.c.) and the mixture kept overnight. *o*-Xylyl bromide (55.5 g.) was then added to it and it was refluxed on a steam-bath for 24 hours. The product was then treated with water. The benzene layer was separated, washed and the benzene evaporated. The liquid remaining was then distilled in *vacuo*, b.p. 148°/5 mm., yield 45 g.

Ethyl γ -(*o*-loly) propane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate (II, R=Me).—To an ice-cold solution of sodium (3.34 g.) in absolute alcohol (70 c.c.) *o*-xylyl malonic ester (38.3 g.) was added and then ethyl bromoacetate (16.5 c.c.) was added drop by drop and the solution kept overnight. The reaction was completed by heating on the water-bath for 3 hours. After the removal of alcohol, it was diluted with water when a heavy oil separated. It was taken up in ether. The ether solution was washed and concentrated. The residual liquid boiled constantly at 186°/5 mm., yield 47 g. or 92% of theory. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 7.4. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 65.1; H, 7.4 per cent).

o-Xylylsuccinic Acid (III, R=Me).—The above product (20 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour with alcoholic potash (30%, 75 c.c.) After the removal of alcohol, it was acidified and kept overnight when a solid acid separated out. It was filtered off, dried on a porous plate and the dry acid heated to 180° in an oil-bath till the evolution of CO₂ ceased. The solid residue obtained on cooling was crystallised from water, m. p. 172° with a little previous shrinkage. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 6.3. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 64.8; H, 6.3 per cent).

The *anhydride*, obtained on heating the acid with acetic anhydride, is a viscous liquid, b.p. 270°/50 mm. The *anilic acid*, prepared from the anhydride and aniline in benzene solution, crystallises from a mixture of benzene and acetone, m.p. 157-58°. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 6.3. $C_{18}H_{19}O_3N$ requires C, 72.7; H, 6.4 per cent).

On heating the anilic acid to 170° for an hour the *anil* was obtained, which crystallises from dilute alcohol, m.p. 114°. (Found: C, 77.2; H, 6.3. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N$ requires C, 77.4; H, 6.1 per cent).

5-Methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic Acid (IV, R=Me).—Finely powdered, dry *o*-xylylsuccinic acid (4 g.) was dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) and kept overnight. The solution was then poured on to crushed ice with stirring when 5-Methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic acid (IV, R=Me) separated out. It crystallises from hot water in colourless shining crystals, m.p. 164°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 5.8. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 70.5; H, 5.8 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallises from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 255°. (Found: C, 59.2; H, 5.8. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N_2$ requires C, 59.7; H, 5.7 per cent)

B. *Rational Synthesis of 5-Methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic Acid (IV, R=Me) from 4-Methyl-1-hydrindone*

β -*o*-Tolylpropionic acid was prepared by hydrolysing *o*-xylylmalonic ester with 25% alcoholic potash. After an hour of refluxing the alcohol was evaporated off with the addition of water and the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid and kept overnight. The separated solid acid was collected, dried and then heated to 160-70° for about 2 hours till the evolution of carbon dioxide ceased. The product obtained on cooling was crystallised from water in thin shining plates, m. p. 103° (melting point given by Young is 102° and by Mercer and Robertson is 104-105°).

4-Methyl-1-hydrindone (VI).—The dry acid obtained above (27 g.) was heated to 50° for 1 hour with thionyl chloride (14.5 c.c.). The last traces of thionyl chloride were then removed *in vacuo* at 50-60° and the acid chloride of β -*o*-tolylpropionic acid (28 g.) was fractionated at 96°/5 mm. Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (35 g.) was added in three portions to the acid chloride in dry petroleum ether (80 c.c.), the flask being heated in warm water after each addition and shaken. It was then heated on a water-bath for about 3 hours with frequent shaking, at least half the volume of petroleum ether was allowed to escape through the condenser during this time. It was then decomposed with ice, acidified with hydrochloric acid, and heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. It was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution to remove acidic product. On evaporation of the ether, the solid residue was distilled at 120°/5 mm., yield 12.5 g. *4-Methyl-1-hydrindone (VI)* crystallises in fine needles from petroleum ether or dilute acetone, m. p. 101-102°. The yield of (VI) by the cyclisation of *o*-xylylsuccinic acid (III, R=Me) by Young's method (*loc. cit.*) is less than 25% and the m. p. given by him is 95°. Mercer and Robertson (*loc. cit.*) prepared the ketone (m. p. 103-4°) by the cyclisation of the acid chloride in benzene solution but they did not mention the yield. (Found: C, 81.7; H, 6.7. C₁₀H₁₀O requires C, 82.1; H, 6.8 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* crystallises from dilute alcohol in almost colourless crystals which become yellow to orange in presence of light, m.p. 139° (decomp.), m.p. given by Young is 133°. (Found: C, 81.0; H, 6.7. C₁₁H₁₀N₂ requires C, 81.3; H, 6.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallises from dilute acetic acid decomposing at 260°. (Found: C, 64.6; H, 6.4. C₁₁H₁₀ON₂ requires C, 65.0; H, 6.4 per cent).

1-Methylbenzene-2- β -propionic)-3-carboxylic Acid (VIII).—The formyl derivative of the methylhydrindone was prepared by adding the ketonic substance (6 g.) to a suspension of finely divided sodium (4 g.) in dry benzene (120 c.c.) and shaken in the cold till it went into solution. Ethyl formate (11 c.c.) was then added and after keeping overnight, it was treated with ice-water, the benzene layer separated and the aqueous layer extracted once with ether. The aqueous solution was then acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid when a light yellow precipitate was obtained. It was filtered and washed well with water, yield 6.5 g. It gave a red-lish violet colouration with ferric chloride and went into solution in dilute aqueous sodium carbonate or sodium hydroxide with a pink colour. As the hydroxymethylene compound gave difficulty in crystallisation it was directly converted into the cyanoketone.

The above product (6.5 g.) was heated to 70° with glacial acetic acid (300 c.c.) and powdered hydroxylamine hydrochloride (5 g.) was stirred in. After 15 minutes, the solution was cooled, diluted and the orange-red solid filtered, washed well with water and dried on a porous plate. The crude cyanoketone (6 g.), thus obtained, was dissolved in a solution of caustic potash (16 g.) in spirit (16 c.c.), and water (16 c.c.) and heated in a steam-bath for 60 hours

and then a further quantity of potash (16 g. in 16 c.c. of water) was added and the heating was continued for 80-90 hours till the evolution of ammonia ceased. The mixture was diluted with water, filtered and the filtrate acidified when an acid was precipitated. This was purified by dissolving in dilute sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitation with acid when the sparingly soluble *1-methylbenzene-2-(β-propionic)-3-carboxylic acid* (VIII) was obtained, yield 2.8 g. It crystallised from hot water, m. p. 172°. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 5.7. Equiv., 104.4. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4$ requires C, 63.4; H, 5.7 per cent. Equiv., 104).

The *diethyl ester* was prepared by refluxing the above acid (2.5 g.) for 12-14 hours with absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (0.75 c.c.). It was then diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water. The solvent was then evaporated and the residual liquid distilled at 150°/5 mm., yield 2.55 g. (Found: C, 67.9; H, 7.4. $C_{13}H_{19}O_4$ requires C, 68.1; H, 7.5 per cent).

The *Tricarboxylic Acid* (X).—The above ester (2.4 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 3 hours with finely divided sodium (0.25 g.) in benzene (7 c.c.) when the whole product solidified. It was cooled in ice, ethyl bromoacetate (1.2 c.c.) was added and kept overnight. It was then refluxed on the water-bath for 20 hours, cooled and treated with water. The benzene layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted once with ether. The benzene-ethereal extract was washed with water and the solvent evaporated. The crude product, thus obtained, was hydrolysed by heating on a water-bath for 3 hours with 20% alcoholic potash. The alcohol was then evaporated with the addition of water. After separation of any neutral impurity present by extraction with ether, the aqueous solution was acidified when the acid (X) was precipitated, yield 1.9 g. It crystallises from hot water, m.p. 217-18°. (Found: C, 58.2; H, 5.2. $C_{12}H_{11}O_6$ requires C, 58.6; H, 5.2 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* of the above tricarboxylic acid was prepared by heating the dry acid (1.5 g.) on the water-bath for 20 hours with absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (0.75 c.c.). It was then worked up and distilled in the usual way. It boils at 178°/4 mm., yield 1.45 g. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 7.2. $C_{13}H_{19}O_6$ requires C, 65.1; H, 7.4 per cent).

5-Methyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic Acid (IV, R=Me).—The above tri-ethyl ester (1.35 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 4 hours with molecular sodium (0.1 g.) in benzene (5 c.c.). It was then cooled, treated with ice-water and acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed and the benzene evaporated. The residual oil was then hydrolysed by refluxing on a sand-bath for 15 hours with excess of 6% hydrochloric acid. The solution was then neutralised with soda and extracted with ether to remove some neutral matter. The aqueous solution was then acidified when a crystalline acid was precipitated. After two crystallisations from hot water it melted at 164°. No depression of the m.p. took place on mixing it with the keto-acid obtained by the cyclisation of *o*-xylylsuccinic acid with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 70.3; H, 5.8. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4$ requires C, 70.5; H, 5.8 per cent).

C. Synthesis of 1-Methyl-7-isopropyl-naphthalene (Eudalene)

5-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3-carboxylic Acid (XI).—The keto-acid (IV, R=Me) (4.7 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 40 hours with concentrated hydrochloric

acid (40 c.c.) and amalgamated granulated zinc (35 g.). It was diluted with water, extracted with ether and the solid residue (3.6 g.) obtained on evaporation of the ether crystallised from water in fine needles, m.p. 132°. (Found: C, 75.6; H, 7.3. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.8; H, 7.3 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared in the usual way by heating the acid (6.1 g.) on the water-bath for 10-12 hours with absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 c.c.). It was then diluted with water and the separated oil taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water, and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. The solvent was then evaporated. The residual liquid boiled constantly at 132°/4 mm., yield 5.9 g. (Found: C, 76.7; H, 8.2. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 77.0; H, 8.2 per cent).

The *Alcohol* (XII).—The above ester (5.7 g.) in dry ether (10 c.c.) was added drop by drop to ice-cold methyl magnesium iodide, prepared from magnesium filings (1.9 g.), methyl iodide (5.6 c.c.) and dry ether (40 c.c.). It was kept overnight and then refluxed for 1 hour with shaking from time to time. It was decomposed with crushed ice and acidified with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous portion extracted with ether. The ether was then evaporated and the residual viscous liquid (5 g.) was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour with 10% alcoholic caustic potash to hydrolyse any unchanged ester. The alcohol was evaporated off with the addition of water. The alkaline solution was extracted with ether and the ether evaporated after drying the extract over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residual oil was distilled *in vacuo* when a highly viscous sweet-scented liquid was obtained boiling at 145°/5 mm., yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 81.8; H, 9.8. $C_{14}H_{20}O$ requires C, 82.3; H, 9.8 per cent).

Eudalene (XIII).—The above alcohol (4 g.) was heated in a nitrate-bath with selenium (5 g.), the temperature of the bath being gradually raised from 230° to 300° during 24 hours. When cold, the product was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution filtered and dried. The ether was then evaporated, the residual liquid heated for 1 hour at 240° over sodium under reduced pressure and distilled when eudalene was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 109°/5 mm., yield 2.8 g. It was converted into its *picrate**, orange-yellow needles, m.p. 93°. (Found: C, 57.8; H, 4.6. $C_{20}H_{26}O_7N_2$ requires C, 58.1; H, 4.6 per cent).

Pure eudalene was obtained by decomposing the picrate with dilute ammonia and extracting the liberated oil with ether. The residual liquid obtained on evaporation of the solvent boiled constantly at 112°/6 mm. (Found: C, 90.8; H, 8.66. $C_{14}H_{18}$ requires C, 91.3; H, 8.69 per cent). It had d_4^{20} , 0.9740; n_D^{20} , 1.5833; $[R_L]_D$, 63.2.

The *stypnate* was readily obtained by heating for a few minutes an alcoholic solution of stypnic acid and eudalene in theoretical quantities. It crystallises from spirit in yellow needles, m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 55.8; H, 4.4. $C_{20}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires C, 55.9; H, 4.4 per cent).

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* The picrate, m.p. 92°, has also been prepared by Chatterjee and Bose (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 2.) by a different route.